

Toxicity modeling of aliphatic ethers using topological and information indices[†]

Basheerulla Shaik^a, Jyoti Singh^b, Izhar Ahmad^c and Vijay K. Agrawal*

^aDepartment of Applied Science, National Institute of Technical Teachers' Training & Research, Shamla Hills, Bhopal-462 002, Madhya Pradesh, India

E-mail : basheerulla.81@gmail.com

^bDepartment of SHM, Amrapali Institute of Technology & Sciences, Shiksha Nagar, Lamachaur, Haldwani-263 139, Uttarakhand, India

E-mail : jyotisingh.dtu@gmail.com

^cQSAR and Computer Chemical Laboratories, A. P. S. University, Rewa-486 003, Madhya Pradesh, India

Manuscript received 01 November 2010, accepted 02 November 2010

Abstract : The paper describes QSTR study for prediction of toxicity of a set of 21 aliphatic ethers. A detailed regression analysis of the training and test sets indicated that the best model is the two variable model for modeling the toxicity. The results are critically discussed using variety of statistical parameters.

Keywords : Aliphatic ethers, information and topological indices, QSTR, toxicity.

1. Introduction

Of-late it has been known that some of the chemicals are affecting the environment very badly due to their toxic properties. These toxic materials are found to be dangerous pollutants of environment. Due to this reason, the assessment of toxicity of chemicals is essential. However, experimental estimation of toxicity is cumbersome and time consuming. However, the recent studies indicated that toxicity is well modeled using molecular descriptors and this methodology is proved as a better choice. There are a number of quantitative structure-toxicity relationship (QSTR) studies in literature based on a variety of molecular descriptors including topological indices¹⁻⁴.

It has been found that Trinajstić⁵ has calculated vertex-connectivity index, first- and second-order connectivities (${}^1\chi^v$ and ${}^2\chi^v$), weighted identification number (WID), electronic index (E) and Balaban and Balaban type indices (J and J_{het}) for 21 aliphatic ethers used in the present

study. Using CROMRsel modeling they obtained the following one-, two- and three-variable models.

The models obtained by Trinajstić *et al.*⁵ are reported below :

1.1. The best single-descriptor model

$$\text{pC} = 0.60 (\pm 0.17) + 0.325 (\pm 0.027) \text{WID} \quad (1)$$
$$n = 21, R_{\text{fit}} = 0.942, R_{\text{cv}} = 0.918, S_{\text{fit}} = 0.14, S_{\text{cv}} = 0.17, F = 149$$

1.2. The best two-descriptor model

$$\text{pC} = 0.21 (\pm 0.17) + 0.465 (\pm 0.053) {}^1\chi^v + 0.415 (\pm 0.078) \text{J} \quad (2)$$
$$n = 21, R_{\text{fit}} = 0.967, R_{\text{cv}} = 0.951, S_{\text{fit}} = 0.11, S_{\text{cv}} = 0.14, F = 126 (16)$$

1.3. The best three-descriptor model

$$\text{pC} = 0.75 (\pm 0.13) + 0.328 (\pm 0.046) {}^1\chi^v + 1.83 (\pm 0.34) \text{J} - 1.25 (\pm 0.28) J_{\text{het}} \quad (3)$$

[†]In honour of Professor Padmakar V. Khadikar.

*Present address : Director, National Institute of Technical Teachers' Training and Research, Shamla Hills, Bhopal-462 002, Madhya Pradesh, India.

E-mail : apsvka@yahoo.co.in

$$n = 21, R_{\text{fit}} = 0.981, R_{\text{cv}} = 0.968, S_{\text{fit}} = 0.09, S_{\text{cv}} = 0.11, F = 147 \quad (17)$$

Trinajstić and co-workers⁵ observed that the best model is the aforementioned three-variable model (eq. 3). Furthermore, they argued that their three-variable model is a better model compared to other QSAR models reported in literature⁶. It is worthy to mention that Trinajstić and co-workers⁵ have not divided the dataset into training or test sets for modeling pC.

The present study made by us and reported herein takes accounts of training and test sets. It is worthy to mention that Ockham's Razer principle, frequently called as the principle of economy believes that there is always a compartment for a better choice. Therefore, the main objective of our present investigation is to propose better model. For this purpose we have used the following descriptors.

2. Parameters used : Information-theoretic topological indices

Information-theoretic topological indices are calculated by the application of information theoretic concepts on chemical graphs^{7-10,12,13}. An appropriate set A of n elements is derived from a graph G depending upon certain structural characteristics. On the basis of an equivalence relation defined on A, the set A is partitioned into disjoint subsets A_i of order n_i (i = 1, 2, ..., h; Σ_i n_i = n). A probability distribution is then assigned to the set of equivalence classes :

$$A_1, A_2, \dots, A_h \\ p_1, p_2, \dots, p_h \quad (4)$$

where p_i = n_i/n is the probability that a randomly selected element of A will occur in the i-th subset.

The mean information content of an element of A is defined by Shannon's relation¹¹ :

$$IC = -\sum_{i=1}^h p_i \log p_i \quad (5)$$

The logarithm is taken at base 2 for measuring the information content in bits. The total information content of the set A is then n times IC.

2.1. Mean information content index (^kIC)

Definition :

$${}^kIC = -\sum_{i=1}^h \frac{n_i}{n} \log_2 \frac{n_i}{n} \quad (6)$$

n_i - number of atoms in the i-th class

n - the total number of atoms in the molecule

k - number of atomic layers in the coordination sphere around a given atom that are accounted for

2.2. Structural information content index (^kSIC)

Definition :

$${}^kSIC = {}^kIC / \log_2 n \quad (7)$$

$${}^kIC = -\sum_{i=1}^h \frac{n_i}{n} \log_2 \frac{n_i}{n}$$

n_i - number of atoms in the i-th class

n - the total number of atoms in the molecule

k - number of atomic layers in the coordination sphere around a given atom that are accounted for

2.3. Complementary information content index (^kCIC)

Definition :

$${}^kCIC = \log_2 n - {}^kIC \quad (8)$$

$${}^kIC = -\sum_{i=1}^h \frac{n_i}{n} \log_2 \frac{n_i}{n}$$

n_i - number of atoms in the i-th class

n - the total number of atoms in the molecule

k - number of atomic layers in the coordination sphere around a given atom that are accounted for

2.4. Bonding information content index (^kBIC)

Definition :

$${}^kBIC = {}^kIC / \log_2 q \quad (9)$$

$${}^kIC = -\sum_{i=1}^h \frac{n_i}{n} \log_2 \frac{n_i}{n}$$

n_i - number of atoms in the i-th class

n - the total number of atoms in the molecule

k - number of atomic layers in the coordination sphere around a given atom that are accounted for

q - number of edges in the molecular graph

2.5. Wiener index (W)

Wiener introduced one of the first topological indices for organic molecules in 1947. The Wiener index belongs to the first generation of topological descriptors¹⁴. The path number *W* is defined as the sum of the numbers of edges in the shortest paths in a chemical graph between all pairs of non-hydrogen atoms in a molecule.

The Wiener index *W* is defined as :

$$W = \frac{1}{2} \sum_{(i,j)}^{N_{SA}} d_{ij} \quad (10)$$

d_{ij} - the number of bonds in the shortest path connecting the pair of atoms *i* and *j*

N_{SA} - the number of non-hydrogen atom in the molecule

2.6. Balaban's J index

The average distance sum connectivity index *J* of the molecular graph *G* is defined by the formula¹⁵

$$J = \frac{q}{\mu + 1} \sum_{edges\ ij} (S_i S_j)^{-1/2} \quad (11)$$

q - number of edges in the molecular graph

$m = (q - n + 1)$ - the cyclomatic number of the molecular graph

n - number of atoms in the molecular graph

S_i - distance sums calculated as the sums over the rows or columns of the topological distance matrix of the molecule, *D*.

2.7. Balaban heteroatom index (J_{het})

This is an extension of Balaban index (*J*)^{15,16} to molecules containing heteroatoms. In the case of heteroatoms differentiation is made between the atoms of different kinds by modifying the corresponding elements of the distance matrix *D*. For instance, the following modification was suggested for the diagonal elements :

$$(D)_{ii} = 1 - (Z_c/Z_i) \quad (12)$$

where $Z_c = 6$ and Z_i is determined by the number of all electrons of atom *i* or namely Z_i is the atomic number of given elements.

The off-diagonal elements of the modified distance matrix for heteroatom systems are given by the following

equation :

$$(D)_{ij} = \sum k_r r \quad (13)$$

where the summation is over *r* bonds.

The bond parameter k_r is given by the following expression :

$$k_r = 1/ w_r X (Z_c)^2 / (Z_i + Z_j)$$

where w_r is the bond weight with values of 1, 1.5, 2 and 3 for single, an aromatic, double and triple bond respectively.

3. Presentation of data

The ethers under present study along with their toxicity values (pC) have been reported in Table 1. We have calculated all the topological and information theoretic indices using DRAGON software¹⁷ and they are recorded

Table 1. Ethers used in the present study with their toxicity values (pC)

Sl. no.	Ethers	pC
1.*	Dimethyl	1.430
2.	Methyl ethyl	1.740
3.*	Methyl propyl	2.450
4.	Methyl isopropyl	2.260
5.	Methyl butyl	2.700
6.*	Methyl isobutyl	2.790
7	Methyl sec-butyl	2.790
8.	Methyl tert-butyl	2.790
9.*	Methyl pentyl	2.880
10.	Diethyl	2.220
11.	Ethyl propyl	2.600
12.*	Ethyl isopropyl	2.600
13.	Ethyl butyl	2.820
14.	Ethyl isobutyl	2.820
15.*	Ethyl sec-butyl	2.850
16.	Ethyl tert-butyl	2.920
17.	Ethyl pentyl	3.000
18.*	Ethyl tert-pentyl	3.150
19.	Dipropyl	2.790
20.	Propyl isopropyl	2.820
21.*	Di-isopropyl	2.820

*For test set.

in Table 2. The information indices involved in modeling are 0I_C , 0SIC , 0CIC , 0BIC , other topological indices used includes : Wiener (*W*) and Balaban (*J*), Balaban type (J_{hetZ} , J_{hetm} , J_{hetv} , J_{hete} , J_{hetp}). The results obtained by us following successive regression are given below :

Table 2. Values of calculated information and topological indices

Compd. no.	${}^0\text{IC}$	${}^0\text{SIC}$	${}^0\text{CIC}$	${}^0\text{BIC}$	W	J	J_{hetZ}	J_{hetm}	J_{hetv}	J_{hetc}	J_{hetp}
1	1.224	0.386	1.946	0.408	4.000	1.633	2.177	2.176	0.836	2.167	0.742
2	1.189	0.332	2.396	0.344	10.000	1.975	2.413	2.412	1.171	2.406	1.060
3	1.159	0.297	2.748	0.304	20.000	2.191	2.506	2.505	1.489	2.501	1.377
4	1.159	0.297	2.748	0.304	18.000	2.540	2.973	2.972	1.644	2.966	1.508
5	1.135	0.272	3.035	0.278	35.000	2.339	2.569	2.569	1.754	2.566	1.649
6	1.135	0.272	3.035	0.278	32.000	2.627	2.918	2.917	1.916	2.913	1.792
7	1.135	0.272	3.035	0.278	31.000	2.754	3.085	3.084	1.974	3.079	1.841
8	1.135	0.272	3.035	0.278	28.000	3.168	3.609	3.607	2.183	3.602	2.024
9	1.116	0.254	3.277	0.258	56.000	2.447	2.622	2.621	1.964	2.619	1.870
10	1.159	0.297	2.748	0.304	20.000	2.191	2.620	2.619	1.351	2.613	1.230
11	1.135	0.272	3.035	0.278	35.000	2.339	2.694	2.693	1.562	2.689	1.439
12	1.135	0.272	3.035	0.278	32.000	2.627	3.082	3.081	1.687	3.075	1.545
13	1.116	0.254	3.277	0.258	56.000	2.447	2.732	2.731	1.760	2.727	1.642
14	1.116	0.254	3.277	0.258	52.000	2.678	3.019	3.018	1.880	3.013	1.747
15	1.116	0.254	3.277	0.258	50.000	2.832	3.220	3.219	1.951	3.214	1.807
16	1.116	0.254	3.277	0.258	46.000	3.154	3.639	3.637	2.104	3.631	1.938
17	1.099	0.240	3.485	0.243	84.000	2.530	2.758	2.757	1.933	2.755	1.824
18	1.099	0.240	3.485	0.243	71.000	3.112	3.456	3.455	2.266	3.451	2.119
19	1.116	0.254	3.277	0.258	56.000	2.447	2.776	2.775	1.690	2.771	1.565
20	1.116	0.254	3.277	0.258	52.000	2.678	3.077	3.075	1.797	3.070	1.657
21	1.116	0.254	3.277	0.258	48.000	2.953	3.444	3.442	1.918	3.436	1.760

3.1. One-variable model

The one-variable models using NCSS software were found as below.

$$pC = 1.0907 (\pm 0.0621) {}^0\text{CIC} - 0.6927 \quad (14)$$

$$n = 21, R^2 = 0.9419, \text{Se} = 0.1023, F = 308.057, Q = 9.4870$$

$$\text{PRESS/SSY} = 0.0616, R^2_{\text{CV}} = 0.9383, S_{\text{PRESS}} = 0.1023, \text{PSE} = 0.0973, \text{PE} = 0.0084$$

$$pC = -11.8510 (\pm 0.6601) {}^0\text{SIC} + 5.8771 \quad (15)$$

$$n = 21, R^2 = 0.9443, \text{Se} = 0.1001, F = 322.286, Q = 9.7078$$

$$\text{PRESS/SSY} = 0.0589, R^2_{\text{CV}} = 0.9410, S_{\text{PRESS}} = 0.1001, \text{PSE} = 0.0952, \text{PE} = 0.0081$$

$$pC = -13.4058 (\pm 0.7307) {}^0\text{IC} + 17.8403 \quad (16)$$

$$n = 21, R^2 = 0.9466, \text{Se} = 0.0981, F = 336.575, Q = 9.9178$$

$$\text{PRESS/SSY} = 0.0564, R^2_{\text{CV}} = 0.9435, S_{\text{PRESS}} = 0.0981, \text{PSE} = 0.0933, \text{PE} = 0.0074$$

We observed that the one-variable model using ${}^0\text{IC}$ (eq. 16) as the correlating parameter is the best among the three attempted one-variable models.

3.2. Two-variable model

Successive regressions yielded several two variable models (Table 3) and the model given below is found to be the best among two-variable models.

$$pC = -9.1037 (\pm 1.0285) {}^0\text{IC} + 0.4538 (\pm 0.0949) J_{\text{hetp}} + 12.2215 \quad (17)$$

$$n = 21, R^2 = 0.9765, R^2_{\text{A}} = 0.9738, \text{Se} = 0.0669, F = 373.357, Q = 14.7710$$

$$\text{PRESS/SSY} = 0.0240, R^2_{\text{CV}} = 0.9759, S_{\text{PRESS}} = 0.0669, \text{PSE} = 0.0619, \text{PE} = 0.0034$$

3.3. Three-variable model

Further regression analysis gave several three-variable models (Table 3) and the one given below is found to be the best three-variable model.

Table 3. Regression parameters and quality of correlation for modeling entire set of 21 compounds

Model no.	Parameters used	A _i = (1---3)	B	R ²	R ² _{Adj}	Se	F-ratio	Q = R/Se
1	J _{hetv}	1.1406 (±0.1037)	0.6301	0.8643	-	0.1564	121.007	5.9442
2	J _{hetp}	1.1888 (±0.1036)	0.6980	0.8740	-	0.1507	131.805	6.2036
3	⁰ BIC	-10.5566 (±0.6207)	5.5873	0.9384	-	0.1054	289.260	9.1908
4	⁰ CIC	1.0907 (±0.0621)	-0.6927	0.9419	-	0.1023	308.057	9.4870
5	⁰ SIC	-11.8510 (±0.6601)	5.8771	0.9443	-	0.1001	322.286	9.7078
6	⁰ IC	-13.4058 (±0.7307)	17.8403	0.9466	-	0.0981	336.575	9.9178
7	⁰ SIC	-59.3706 (±23.0330)	6.9971	0.9550	0.9500	0.0925	190.916	10.5648
	⁰ BIC	42.4785 (±20.5823)						
8	⁰ IC	-153.7234 (±37.6105)	211.9173	0.9699	0.9665	0.0757	289.703	13.0097
	⁰ CIC	-11.4459 (±3.0676)						
9	⁰ SIC	-8.0121 (±0.9551)	4.0827	0.9743	0.9715	0.0698	341.682	14.1414
	J _{hetp}	0.4569 (±0.0996)						
10	⁰ IC	-9.3053 (±1.0440)	12.4522	0.9749	0.9721	0.0690	350.030	14.3097
	J _{hetv}	0.4195 (±0.0930)						
11	⁰ IC	-9.1037 (±1.0285)	12.2215	0.9765	0.9738	0.0669	373.357	14.7710
	J _{hetp}	0.4538 (±0.0949)						
12	⁰ IC	-10.9784 (±1.8169)	14.5246	0.9784	0.9746	0.0659	256.960	15.0097
	W	-0.0023 (±0.0018)						
	J _{hetp}	0.4018 (±0.1025)						
13	⁰ IC	-8.7493 (±1.0391)	11.8865	0.9787	0.9750	0.0654	260.992	15.1268
	J _{hetZ}	-0.0827 (±0.0612)						
	J _{hetp}	0.5614 (±0.1222)						
14	⁰ IC	-113.1097 (±27.5568)	155.9674	0.9863	0.9839	0.0524	409.233	18.9528
	⁰ CIC	-8.4004 (±2.2291)						
	J _{hetv}	0.3353 (±0.0741)						
15	⁰ IC	-110.5557 (±26.6889)	152.4746	0.9873	0.9850	0.0506	439.879	19.6370
	⁰ CIC	-8.2065 (±2.1580)						
	J _{hetp}	0.3645 (±0.0755)						

$$\begin{aligned}
 pC = & -110.5557 (\pm 26.6889) {}^0IC \\
 & + 0.3645 (\pm 0.0755) J_{hetp} - 8.2065 \\
 & (\pm 2.1580) {}^0CIC + 152.4746 \quad (18)
 \end{aligned}$$

n = 21, R² = 0.9873, R²_A = 0.9850, Se = 0.0506, F = 439.879, Q = 19.6370

PRESS/SSY = 0.0128, R²_{CV} = 0.9871, S_{PRESS} = 0.0505, PSE = 0.0455, PE = 0.0018

We have reported all the derived models for the entire set of 21 compounds in Table 3. The qualities of these models are also recorded in this Table 3. On the basis of Pogliani's Quality factor (Q) which is a ratio of R and Se, it may be concluded that the three-variable model expressed in eq. (18) [model 15 (Table 3)] is the best for

modeling the toxicity value pC of the compounds under investigation.

Finally, we have calculated pC values for the 21 ethers using model 11 (Table 3) and model 15 (Table 3). Such values are reported in Table 5. The residual value clearly indicates that the model 15 (Table 3) is the best for modeling pC values. Further confirmation is obtained by plotting a graph between observed and estimated pC values for these two models. Such comparison is demonstrated in Figs. 1 and 2 respectively. The predicted R² value 0.9873 for model 15 (Table 3) confirms our finding. Further estimation of predictive power is made by calculating the cross-validated parameters¹⁸ which are summarized in Table 4.

Fig. 1. Correlation between observed vs estimated pC values using model 11 (Table 3).

Fig. 2. Correlation between observed vs estimated pC values using model 15 (Table 3).

Table 4. Cross validated parameters for the model given in Table 4

Model no.	Parameters used	PRESS/SSY	R^2_{CV}	S _{PRESS}	PSE	PE	6PE
1	J_{hetv}	0.1570	0.8429	0.1564	0.1487	0.0197	0.1184
2	J_{hetp}	0.1441	0.8558	0.1507	0.1433	0.0183	0.1099
3	0BIC	0.0656	0.9343	0.1054	0.1002	0.0089	0.0537
4	0CIC	0.0616	0.9383	0.1023	0.0973	0.0084	0.0507
5	0SIC	0.0589	0.9410	0.1001	0.0952	0.0081	0.0486
6	0IC	0.0564	0.9435	0.0981	0.0933	0.0074	0.0466
7	0SIC	0.0471	0.9528	0.0925	0.0856	0.0065	0.0392
8	0BIC	0.0310	0.9689	0.0757	0.0701	0.0043	0.0262
	0IC						
	0CIC						

9	⁰ SIC	0.0263	0.9736	0.0698	0.0646	0.0037	0.0224
	J _{hetp}						
10	⁰ IC	0.0256	0.9743	0.0690	0.0639	0.0036	0.0216
	J _{hetv}						
11	⁰ IC	0.0240	0.9759	0.0669	0.0619	0.0034	0.0205
	J _{hetp}						
12	⁰ IC	0.0220	0.9779	0.0659	0.0593	0.0031	0.0188
	W						
	J _{hetp}						
13	⁰ IC	0.0216	0.9783	0.0653	0.0588	0.0030	0.0185
	J _{hetZ}						
	J _{hetp}						
14	⁰ IC	0.0138	0.9861	0.0524	0.0471	0.0029	0.0119
	⁰ CIC						
	J _{hetv}						
15	⁰ IC	0.0128	0.9871	0.0505	0.0455	0.0018	0.0110
	⁰ CIC						
	J _{hetp}						

Table 5. Values of observed and estimated pC values using eqs. (17) and (18) (Model 11 and 15, Table 3)

Compd. no.	Observed pC	Using model 11		Using model 15	
		Estimated pC	Residual	Estimated pC	Residual
1	1.430	1.415	0.015	1.455	-0.025
2	1.740	1.878	-0.138	1.747	-0.007
3	2.450	2.295	0.155	2.291	0.159
4	2.260	2.355	-0.095	2.339	-0.079
5	2.700	2.637	0.063	2.688	0.012
6	2.790	2.702	0.088	2.740	0.050
7	2.790	2.724	0.066	2.758	0.032
8	2.790	2.807	-0.017	2.825	-0.035
9	2.880	2.911	-0.031	2.883	-0.003
10	2.220	2.229	-0.009	2.237	-0.017
11	2.600	2.542	0.058	2.612	-0.012
12	2.600	2.590	0.010	2.650	-0.050
13	2.820	2.807	0.013	2.800	0.020
14	2.820	2.855	-0.035	2.838	-0.018
15	2.850	2.882	-0.032	2.860	-0.010
16	2.920	2.941	-0.021	2.908	0.012
17	3.000	3.044	-0.044	3.039	-0.039
18	3.150	3.178	-0.028	3.147	0.003
19	2.790	2.772	0.018	2.772	0.018
20	2.820	2.814	0.006	2.806	0.014
21	2.820	2.861	-0.041	2.843	-0.023

4. Confirmation on the basis of cross validation

The predictive power for all the proposed models was carried out by the leave-one-out cross validation procedure and the same are reported in Table 4. The ratio PRESS/SSY can be used to calculate approximate confidence intervals of prediction of new compounds. PRESS is a good estimate of the real predictive power of the model. If PRESS is smaller than SSY, the model predicts better than chance and can be considered statistically significant.

To be a reasonable and significant QSAR model the ratio PRESS/SSY should be less than 0.4 (PRESS/SSY < 0.4) and the value of this ratio smaller than 0.1 indicates an excellent model. A close observation of Table 4 showing all the models have the PRESS/SSY ratio more or less or nearer to 0.1 this indicating that all the proposed models are have best predicting capacity. R^2_{CV} is the cross validated squared correlation coefficient. The highest R^2_{CV} value for three-parametric model contains ⁰IC, J_{hetp}, and ⁰CIC as correlating parameters (eq. 18) uncertainty in prediction (S_{PRESS}) and predictive squared error (PSE) were also calculated a perusal of Table 4 shows that S_{PRESS} coincides with SE. This cross-validated parameter, i.e. S_{PRESS} is of no value in judging uncertainty of the prediction. Therefore, another cross-validated parameter related to uncertainty of prediction, the PSE, is calculated. The lowest value of PSE for eq. (18) supports its highest predictive potential. We have also calculated

PE (Predictive error of coefficient) value of the proposed models and were reported in Table 4. It is argued that if

- (a) $R < PE$, then correlation is not significant;
- (b) $R > PE$, several times (at least three times), then correlation is significant; and if
- (c) $R > 6PE$, then the correlation is definitely excellent.

The cross validated data presented in Table 4 indicates that R is much larger than $6PE$ indicating that the models discussed above possess high degree of correlation.

5. Randic recommendations

Randic^{19,20} stated that if a descriptor strongly correlates with another descriptor already used in a regression, then that should be discarded they should not be used simultaneously in multi-parametric modeling. For example, $^1\chi^v$ and $^2\chi^v$. $^1\chi^v$ very often strongly correlates and in many structure-property-activity studies with $^2\chi^v$ it therefore the latter is discarded. This is not theoretically justified and despite the widespread practice this should be stopped. Although two highly correlated descriptors overall depict the same features of molecular structure. It is important to recognize that even highly interrelated descriptors differ in some other structural traits. The difference between them may be relatively small, but nevertheless very important for structure-property regression.

The criteria for inclusion or exclusion of descriptors should not be based on parallelism between descriptors even if overwhelming, but should be based on whether the part in which two descriptors disagree is or is not relevant for the characterization of the property considered. If the part in which the second descriptor differs from the first, regardless of how small it is, is relevant for the property under consideration, then the descriptor should be included. Randic^{19,20} further stated that the selection of descriptors to be used in structure-property-activity studies should not be delegated solely to computers, although statistical criteria will continue to be useful for preliminary screening of descriptors taken from a large pool. Often in an automated selection of descriptors, a descriptor will be discarded because it is highly correlated with another descriptor already selected. But what is important is not whether two descriptors parallel one another; i.e. duplicates much of the same structural in-

formation, but whether they are complementary in those parts that are important for structure-property-activity correlations. Hence, the residual of the correlation between two descriptors should be examined and kept or discarded depending on how well it can improve the correlation based on already selected descriptors. Hence although 0IC and J_{hetp} are highly correlated they are allowed as their information content are very much different.

In the proposed models we observed that there is 0.01 unit difference between R^2 value for the two- and the three-variable models. We, therefore, thought that perhaps the two variable model is a better model for modeling toxicity. We have confirmed this on the basis of modeling pC using training and test sets. These sets are distinguished by putting a * in Table 1 for test set. The two-variable modeling using the aforementioned parameters (0IC , J_{hetp}) gave the following results.

2.1. Two-variable modeling for the training set

$$pC = -9.6398 (\pm 0.9770) ^0IC + 0.4404 (\pm 0.0937) J_{hetp} + 12.8447 \quad (19)$$

$$n = 14, R^2 = 0.9857, R^2_A = 0.9831, Se = 0.0608, F = 380.100, Q = 16.3293$$

$$PRESS/SSY = 0.0144, R^2_{CV} = 0.9856, S_{PRESS} = 0.0608, PSE = 0.0559, PE = 0.0026$$

2.2. Two-variable modeling for the test set

$$pC = -6.4361 (\pm 3.4689) ^0IC + 0.6417 (\pm 0.3253) J_{hetp} + 8.8986 \quad (20)$$

$$n = 8, R^2 = 0.9860, R^2_A = 0.9804, Se = 0.0732, F = 175.826, Q = 13.5652$$

$$PRESS/SSY = 0.0141, R^2_{CV} = 0.9859, S_{PRESS} = 0.0732, PSE = 0.0578, PE = 0.0032$$

The choice in favor of two-variable modeling can be further made :

- (a) By comparing our and the results of Trinajstić and
- (b) Making three-variable modeling for training and test sets using the same parameters used for modeling toxicity of 21 compounds. R^2 values for two- and three-variables of Trinajstić differ by 0.014, while this difference in our case is of 0.01 R^2 -unit. Furthermore, three-variable modeling of training and test set gave the following results :

5.3. Three-variable modeling for the training set

$$pC = -113.8209 (\pm 18.9928) ^0IC$$

$$+ 0.3351 (\pm 0.0527) J_{\text{hep}} - 8.4304$$

$$(\pm 1.5364) {}^0\text{CIC} + 156.9009 \quad (21)$$

$n = 14$, $R^2 = 0.9964$, $R^2_A = 0.9954$, $Se = 0.0318$, $F = 934.031$, $Q = 31.3899$

$\text{PRESS/SSY} = 0.0035$, $R^2_{\text{CV}} = 0.9965$, $S_{\text{PRESS}} = 0.0319$, $\text{PSE} = 0.0278$, $\text{PE} = 0.0006$

5.4. Three-variable modeling for the test set

$$\text{pC} = -49.8132 (\pm 105.8239) {}^0\text{IC}$$

$$+ 0.6134 (\pm 0.3629) J_{\text{hep}} - 3.4989$$

$$(\pm 8.5304) {}^0\text{CIC} + 66.8176 \quad (22)$$

$n = 8$, $R^2 = 0.9865$, $R^2_A = 0.9765$, $Se = 0.0802$, $F = 97.774$, $Q = 12.3844$

$\text{PRESS/SSY} = 0.0135$, $R^2_{\text{CV}} = 0.9865$, $S_{\text{PRESS}} = 0.0801$, $\text{PSE} = 0.0566$, $\text{PE} = 0.0031$

We observed that the data set for training and test sets while performing the three-variable modeling violates the rule of thumb²¹. This clearly means that the two-variable modeling will be the best for the entire set of 21 compounds as well as for training and test set. In order to confirm this we have estimated pC values for all the three sets and obtained the corresponding predictive correlation coefficient (Figs. 2-4) in all the three cases predictive correlation coefficient are found ≈ 0.98 , thus confirming that the modeling of toxicity of present set of compounds more precisely two-variable is the most appropriate model.

Fig. 3. Correlation between observed vs estimated pC values using eq. (19) (for training set).

Fig. 4. Correlation between observed vs estimated pC values using eq. (19) (for training set).

6. Conclusion

(1) Our study indicates that the best model for modeling the toxicity of the compounds used is the one based on the use of 0IC and J_{hetp} as the correlating parameters.

(2) Our models are better than the models prepared by other workers.

Acknowledgement

Authors are thankful to Prof. P. V. Khadikar eminent topologist who not only gave us suggestions but also enlightened us regarding fascinating field of Topological Modeling.

References

1. V. K. Agrawal, S. Srivastava and P. V. Khadikar, *Mol. Div.*, 2001, **8**, 834.
2. V. K. Agrawal and P. V. Khadikar, *Bioorg. Med. Chem.*, 2002, **10**, 3517.
3. V. K. Agrawal, K. C. Mathur, S. Karmarkar and P. V. Khadikar, *Bulg. Chem. Ind.*, 2002, **73**, 99.
4. V. K. Agrawal and P. V. Khadikar, *Bioorg. Med. Chem.*, 2001, **9**, 3035.
5. A. Miličević, S. Nikolić and N. Trinajstić, *Mol. Div.*, 2006, **10**, 95.
6. M. Randić and S. C. Basak, *J. Chem. Inf. Comput. Sci.*, 2001, **41**, 614.
7. R. Sarkar, A. B. Roy and P. K. Sarkar, *Math. Biosci.*, 1978, **39**, 299.
8. S. C. Basak and V. R. Magnuson, *Arz. Forschu. Drug Res.*, 1983, **33**, 501.
9. D. Bonchev and N. Trinajstić, *J. Chem. Phys.*, 1977, **67**, 4517.
10. A. B. Roy, S. C. Basak, D. K. Harriss, and V. R. Magnuson, X. J. R. Avula, R. E. Kalman, A. L. Liapis and E. Y. Rodin (eds.), "Mathematical Modeling in Science and Technology", Pergamon Press, New York, 1984, 745.
11. C. E. Shannon, *Bell. Sys. Tech. J.*, 1948, **27**, 379.
12. L. B. Kier, *J. Pharm. Sci.*, 1980, **69**, 807.
13. S. C. Basak, D. K. Harriss and V. R. Magnuson, *J. Pharm. Sci.*, 1984, **73**, 429.
14. H. Wiener, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1947, **69**, 17.
15. A. T. Balaban, *Pure Appl. Chem.*, 1983, **55**, 199.
16. A. T. Balaban, *Chem. Phys. Lett.*, 1982, **89**, 399.
17. DRAGON software for calculation of topological indices : www.disat.unimib.it
18. S. Chatterjee, A. S. Hadi and B. Price, "Regression Analysis by Examples", 3rd ed., New York. Wiley Interscience, 2000.
19. M. Randić, *Acta Chim. Slov.*, 1998, **45**, 239.
20. M. Randić, *J. Chem. Inf. Comput. Sci.*, 1977, **37**, 672.
21. M. S. Tuts, N. T. Harper and A. B. Simmonds. "In Advances in Drug Research", eds., Academic Press. London, 1971, **1**, 6.